

Enabling national step changes in bioinformatics through ABLeS, the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share

V3.0
November 15 2023

Ove Johan Ragnar Gustafsson, Ziad Al Bkhetan, Rhys Francis, Steven Manos

Australian BioCommons

University of Melbourne

Melbourne, Australia

www.biocommons.org.au

Contact: steven@biocommons.org.au

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10139651

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

1. Abstract

ABLeS provides a new access mechanism into Australia's nationally funded computational resources. Whereas existing merit allocation schemes provide computational power to the achievement of highly targeted research advances, ABLeS operates at an earlier stage in major science missions. It provides computational power for the creation of the reference data, and its associated interpretative tools, that are subsequently expected to make high priority research endeavours possible.

These reference data and tool requirements surface in life science research because it is a discipline that has those core characteristics. As our ability to leverage molecular analyses has improved, the life sciences have become critically dependent on community agreed reference data assets that need to be produced using significant computational capability. While many species and specific computational methods need tailored reference data, the recent publication by Google of computed protein structures for the protein complements of 48 species is an example of the use of very substantial computational power to create a novel reference data set with broad applicability in life science¹.

A further example is the Genomics of Australia Plants consortium (GAP), who, over the last couple of years, they have leveraged ABLeS resources to combine limited coverage genome sequencing to build the first-ever Australian Angiosperm Tree of Life: this is an evolutionary tree of nearly all Australian flowering plants, covering 1400 unique native plants. This is a foundational resource that will be used to support the classification of Australian angiosperms, conservation and management.

These are key examples of data sets that change the trajectory for scientific advancement, where subsequent activities will build on that data asset to progress the field.

Delivering compute power effectively at such an early stage in the development of new research fields needs a different set of selection criteria, a focus on the achievement of an outcome, and a change in tolerance around the efficiency of infrastructure consumption. This paper describes the evolution of the ABLeS program, reports that this evolution is driven by an improved understanding of its impact, and provides illustrative examples of this impact for research communities and their science missions.

¹ AlphaFold Protein Structure Database <https://alphafold.ebi.ac.uk/>

2. Introduction

The ABLeS (Australian Biocommons Leadership Share) program was established in April 2021 to more readily support data-driven bioinformatics. This effort is supported by the Australian BioCommons in partnership with Bioplatforms Australia², the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI³, Canberra), and the Pawsey Supercomputing Centre (Pawsey⁴, Perth). ABLeS targets established groups and communities that are focused on a common research theme, create reference data and/or software, and have the ability to plan and prioritise a computational research program. The support available includes access to computational and data infrastructure, specialist expertise, support to adopt best practices and share outputs effectively, and a community led and shared repository of bioinformatics software (i.e. tools and workflows).

“The intention of ABLeS is to grow and simultaneously accelerate the capacity of the life sciences community to create, test and optimise best practice bioinformatics software, and apply this software in production bioinformatics at scale, including the creation of reference data (e.g. reference genome assemblies). It produces a flow of visible and robust software assets as well as unique data assets that collectively enables the entire research community to plan and proceed in ways that would otherwise not occur.”

As of August 2023, there were 126 users from 24 institutes, organisations and research groups onboarded to ABLeS and utilising its resources including the shared software repository of more than 100 tools described in section 2.2. Examples of current communities include Threatened Species Initiative (TSI)⁵, Genomics for Australian Plants (GAP)⁶, Australian Amphibian and Reptile Genomics (AusARG)⁷, Zero Childhood Cancer (Zero)⁸, Telethon Kids Institute⁹, and St Vincent’s Institute of Medical Research¹⁰. A list of the active communities is available through the ABLeS webpages¹¹.

3. Responding to challenges in bioinformatics

Access to appropriate and scalable bioinformatics methods and compute resources is key to research in the life sciences. The requirements of bioinformatics can be characterised in the following four ways:

Challenge 1 - Bioinformatics compute use is episodic in nature, and happens over multi-year timeframes as research collaborations plan, prioritise, define collective goals, gather samples, and refine experiments (both laboratory and bioinformatics based);

² Bioplatforms Australia <https://bioplatforms.com/>

³ National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) website - <https://nci.org.au>

⁴ Pawsey Supercomputing Centre website - <https://pawsey.org.au>

⁵ Threatened Species Initiative (TSI) <https://threatenedspeciesinitiative.com/>

⁶ Genomics for Australian Plants (GAP) <https://www.genomicsforaustralianplants.com/>

⁷ Australian Amphibian & Reptile Genomics (AusARG) <https://ausargenomics.com/>

⁸ Zero Childhood Cancer (Zero) <https://www.zerochildhoodcancer.org.au/>

⁹ Telethon Kids Institute <https://www.telethonkids.org.au/>

¹⁰ St Vincent’s Institute of Medical Research (SVI) <https://www.svi.edu.au/>

¹¹ Active ABLeS communities <https://australianbiocommons.github.io/ables/communities/>

Challenge 2 - Compute use is primarily driven by data availability: Compute is required when samples become available and experimental analysis has happened (e.g. genomics sequencing). This reflects the realities of life sciences in that biology is complex, unpredictable and does not respect time tables. Timelines are therefore unknown in advance and subject to delays;

Challenge 3 - Software¹² is diverse: It is often imported, complex, rapidly evolving, multi-language and not optimised for high performance computing (HPC) infrastructure and HPC policies (e.g. queue system policies, efficiency requirements); and

Challenge 4 - Various types of expertise and effective coordination are needed: research software engineers (RSEs¹³) are prominent in bioinformatics, and in practice this diverse group can have significantly different levels of experience and expertise in software and computational systems. A community that promotes, supports and coordinates collaborative effort, and which can onboard less experienced RSEs, is critical to the effective application of bioinformatics in Australia.

These characteristics are not readily supported by existing access schemes such as the National Computational Merit Allocation Scheme (NCMAS¹⁴) and the Adapter Scheme¹⁵, which require upfront plans that are not always possible in sample-driven bioinformatics, are time-limited to a maximum of 12 months, and are generally not supportive of complex software implementations, the optimisations that may be required, and the need to onboard and train bioinformaticians from non-computational research backgrounds.

The ABLeS partnership between the BioCommons, NCI and Pawsey addresses these challenges through the schemes described next.

4. ABLeS schemes

When first conceived in 2021, ABLeS was focussed around the community-based creation of reference data assets. ABLeS has now been extended to more comprehensively support the characteristics of bioinformatics as it is practised, and specifically accelerate the following three schemes (figure 1):

Scheme 1: Creation of reference data assets

Research groups and consortia within the life sciences required dedicated compute capacity to allow them to efficiently construct reference data: these are data assets of enduring value to the research community that underpin and enable downstream research. The key example for many current communities is the reference genome assembly¹⁶.

¹² "Source code files, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows and executables that were created during the research process or for a research purpose.", Gruenpeter, M. et al. (2021). Defining Research Software: a controversial discussion (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5504016>

¹³ "People who combine professional software expertise with an understanding of research", <https://researchsoftware.org/>

¹⁴ National Computational Merit Allocation Scheme (NCMAS) website - <https://my.nci.org.au/mancini/ncmas/2023>

¹⁵ NCI Adapter Scheme - <https://nci.org.au/users/how-access-nci/adapter-scheme>

¹⁶ For example, the Threatened Species Initiative <https://threatenedspeciesinitiative.com/> & Genomics for Australian Plants <https://www.genomicsforaustralianplants.com/>

Scheme 2: Production analysis

Institutes, consortia and core facilities are increasingly facing issues scaling their in-house compute and data infrastructure to the questions, sample sizes, and data set sizes they are addressing as part of their research programs. ABLeS production allocations support these groups to implement and run their computational workflow approaches for omics data analysis at bigger scales.

Scheme 3: Bioinformatics software accelerator

Software accelerator allocations will directly support the further development, installation, optimisation, testing and/or benchmarking of bioinformatics software. These allocations are intended to create a culture of best practice in software, helping bioinformaticians to effectively share and document their work, and make it FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable¹⁷).

This third scheme is a fundamentally new part of ABLeS. A key outcome of the software accelerator is to reduce replication of effort, enable credit to be given to bioinformaticians as RSEs, and ultimately enable more bioinformatics software to execute successfully, efficiently, and at scale on HPC and cloud computing infrastructures. This aspect of ABLeS will be particularly useful for software that requires either high throughput or scale of compute, but also recognises the need for robust software that can be reapplied in the creation of reference data assets and for application of best practice in day-to-day production bioinformatics by facilities or consortia.

¹⁷ Barker, M., Chue Hong, N.P., Katz, D.S. et al. Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. *Sci Data* 9, 622 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>

Figure 1. Pathways within the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (ABLeS), including reference data, production research and software, that are suited for the creation of reference data, implementation of production-level bioinformatics methods and the development and optimisation of research software, respectively. Figure created with yEd¹⁸.

5. Resources, onboarding and support

5.1. Compute and storage resources

ABLeS currently encompasses:

- 16 million service units (SU) of compute capacity and at least 500 TB of storage available per annum on the Gadi supercomputer (NCI resource), and
- 10 million SU of compute capacity and at least 350 TB of storage available per annum on Setonix and Nimbus (Pawsey resources).

The full cost of these resources is being met by the Australian BioCommons, NCI and Pawsey. Access to other resources, such as commercial cloud, are being considered as ABLeS proceeds. To efficiently and fairly utilise the available resources, **Table 1** outlines the default resource allocations and procedures that are in place for the different ABLeS project types.

¹⁸ yEd - graph editor <https://www.yworks.com/products/yed>

Table 1. Default starting resources available to the different types of ABLeS projects.

Resource	ABLeS scheme					
	Reference data		Production bioinformatics		Software accelerator	
	NCI	Pawsey	NCI	Pawsey	NCI	Pawsey
Compute infrastructure	HPC and cloud					
Temporary storage ¹⁹	5 TB	1 PB	5 TB	1 PB	1 TB	1 PB
Project storage ²⁰	5 TB		5 TB		1 TB	
Default service units ²¹	100 kSUs per Quarter		50 kSUs per Quarter		10 kSUs per Quarter	
Time frame	Ongoing				6-12 months	
Specialist support	Yes					
Additional resources	Yes				Yes if the previous usage is > 60%	

To minimise project disruption due to low resources a simple monitoring service checks the available SUs for each project regularly and notifies the project lead when resources are low. The ABLeS project team collaborates with communities to help them reasonably estimate and plan for their SU and storage requirements.

5.2. Bioinformatics support

To mitigate the challenges associated with utilising the provided compute infrastructure, a dedicated *ABLeS Bioinformatics Application Specialist* is available who provides expert support and acts as a coordinator for the support provided by the computational facilities as well as the specialists distributed across the BioCommons.

Cross-cutting challenges that address community-scale computational challenges are prioritised over those which are project-specific.

The specialist's support includes, but is not limited to:

- Onboarding communities, projects and individuals to ABLeS,
- Managing allocations on various infrastructures in collaboration with project leads,
- Assistance with installation and deployment of tools,
- Maintenance of the Australian BioCommons Tools and Workflows repository,
- Management of workflows and databases accessible via NCI and Pawsey, and making these easily accessible by users,

¹⁹ File system that does not have a lifetime for files: i.e. scratch systems

²⁰ File system suitable for storage during the project: i.e. gdata on NCI

²¹ Service Unit (SU) – A measure of computational work. NCI Glossary <https://nci.org.au/media/glossary>

- Workflow optimisation and development, and
- Providing advice and recommendations on administrative and technical issues.

5.3. Supporting best practice software

A central ambition of ABLeS is to create a more consistent experience with bioinformatics tools, workflows and databases across Australia’s two national HPC centres. This ambition will be achieved in two ways.

Firstly, **shared software resources will be explicitly supported by ABLeS**. **Table 2** presents a snapshot of the current approaches used at both NCI and Pawsey. These will be further developed in lock step with the broader BioCommons efforts in this space. As shared software resources are matured or established it is expected that these standardised and supported environments could be beneficial to institutional HPC and other facilities nationally.

Secondly, **ABLeS will support so called connected outcomes** that ensure software is findable, understandable and reusable. As such, guidance in the effective use of standards, services, platforms and methods that support best practice is also explicitly supported, and particularly for those options that achieve this in a straightforward and clear manner.

5.4. Shared software resources

NCI and Pawsey each operate two shared software resources that ABLeS projects can either contribute to or access. **Table 2** highlights these resources, and whether they support installed tools (i.e. modules), containers, workflows and / or databases.

Table 2. Default starting resources available to the different types of ABLeS projects.

Resource	NCI	Pawsey
Installed tools	if89 shared repository	Centrally supported modules
	Centrally supported modules	
Containers	S-HPC ²²	
Workflows	if89 shared repository	Import from findable public repositories
Databases		Central repository on /scratch

NCI bioinformatics tools and workflows

ABLeS, the NCI specialist support team and members of different life science communities have co-created a shared repository (project code if89) of bioinformatics software (tools, workflows) and databases. This is a staging area that allows the community to install virtually any software according to best practices. Any NCI user can access the installations, reducing replication of effort and providing a pathway for NCI staff to identify and migrate community-prioritised software to the set of centrally supported applications, which are supported long-term across all NCI projects.

²² Singularity HPC (S-HPC) <https://singularity-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

- All ABLeS projects at NCI are encouraged to contribute to this repository and guidance material for this process is available²³.
- As of July 2023, 108 bioinformatics software packages are available and can be viewed by any member of the community via the ToolFinder service.
- There are two ways to contribute to this repository. Users can either add software to the repository directly (the preferred approach), or request a software installation via the ABLeS and NCI support teams.

Pawsey bioinformatics tools and workflows

ABLeS and the Pawsey support team ensure that all users of Nimbus²⁴ and Setonix²⁵ can access and contribute to:

- A centrally supported set of installed software,
- A centrally supported set of reference data²⁶, and
- More than 10,000 BioContainers containers, available as though they were already installed centrally as modules. This is achieved through combined use of singularity HPC (S-HPC²⁷), Cern Virtual Machine File System (CVM-FS²⁸) and BioContainers²⁹. This infrastructure combination integrates Pawsey computational systems with best practice international efforts in the container space, which can be contributed to by any Australian researcher through BioConda³⁰.

Users are also encouraged to contribute software to BioConda, as this will generate a BioContainer which can be accessed by anyone globally.

Supporting connected outcomes

ABLeS exists alongside an ecosystem of platforms and services that support making digital outputs findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR)³¹. This ecosystem is detailed below. It is an expectation of the ABLeS program that outputs are shared, and so we encourage people to make use of these supporting platforms, and to help us evolve them in lock step with ABLeS. The aspiration is to make it easier to be FAIR, and thereby reduce replication of effort, support reuse of best practice software and workflows, and give credit to developers within bioinformatics.

Best practice outputs and use of software registration

A key outcome of ABLeS is supporting visible and reusable software. In practice, this means being able to find the software, unambiguously link research outputs (i.e. data) to the software used to create those outputs, and licence that software for reuse. The most straightforward way to do this is by using popular registries that can assign a digital object identifier (DOI), and to assign open source licences, where possible.

²³ Shared repository of bioinformatics software (tools, workflows) and databases

<https://australianbiocommons.github.io/ables/ifa89/>

²⁴ Nimbus <https://pawsey.org.au/systems/nimbus-cloud-service/>

²⁵ Setonix <https://pawsey.org.au/systems/setonix/>

²⁶ <https://support.pawsey.org.au/documentation/display/JS/Life+Science+and+Bioinformatics>

²⁷ Singularity HPC (S-HPC) <https://singularity-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

²⁸ Cern Virtual Machine File System (CVM-FS) <https://cernvm.cern.ch/fs/>

²⁹ BioContainers <https://biocontainers.pro/>

³⁰ Conda <https://docs.conda.io/en/latest/>

³¹ Barker, M., Chue Hong, N.P., Katz, D.S. et al. Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. Sci Data 9, 622 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>

- **Best practice documentation:** Software should be documented such that a new user can understand and reuse that software. ABLeS recommends the use of the BioCommons documentation guidelines for this purpose³².
- **Licensing for software reuse:** ABLeS encourages the use of open source software where possible. Where this is not possible ABLeS will consult with researchers on the best way forward to ensure outputs can be shared with the broader community effectively. For any new software created or modified within the ABLeS program, creators are expected to select an appropriate open source license³³.
- **Software findability:** Community members should be able to unambiguously refer to software versions that they reuse. The ABLeS program encourages all new software packages to be assigned a digital object identifier (DOI): the most straightforward way to do this is by linking GitHub repositories to Zenodo and minting DOIs for each release³⁴. ABLeS will work with researchers to ensure their software is findable according to current best practice.
- **FAIR workflows:** ABLeS recommends one of two available workflow registries: WorkflowHub³⁵ and Dockstore³⁶. Registries allow developers to make their workflows findable, understandable and citable³⁷. This is achieved by integration with the git version control system, wizards that support best practice workflow metadata, and minting DOIs. The Australian BioCommons also administers a space within WorkflowHub³⁸ where any Australian researcher is welcome to create project teams and begin registering workflows. Onboarding support for Dockstore and WorkflowHub is available to all ABLeS projects.

Finding software using ToolFinder service

ToolFinder is an interactive list of available bioinformatics software across the national computational infrastructures in Australia³⁹. It supports the ABLeS program by listing shared software resources at both the NCI and Pawsey.

Workflow execution using Tower service

ABLeS supports several life-science communities utilising the Australian BioCommons Nextflow Tower service⁴⁰ by providing compute infrastructure to run Nextflow pipelines to carry on different bioinformatics analyses. It is a fully subsidised web platform that allows researchers to run and monitor the execution of Nextflow pipelines on various compute infrastructures such as local on-prem, institutional and national HPC platforms, as well as the Azure and AWS clouds.

³² Gustafsson, J., Davis, B., de la Pierre, M., Stott, A., Beecroft, S., Downton, M., Edwards, R., Chew, T., Samaha, G., & Al Bkhetan, Z. Australian BioCommons Documentation Guidelines (Version 1.5.0) [Computer software]

https://github.com/AustralianBioCommons/doc_guidelines

³³ Choose an open source license <https://choosealicense.com/>

³⁴ GitHub integration documentation <https://developers.zenodo.org/#github>

³⁵ Goble C. *et al.* (2021). Implementing FAIR Digital Objects in the EOSC-Life Workflow Collaboratory. Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/4605654>

³⁶ O'Connor BD, Yuen D, Chung V et al. The Dockstore: enabling modular, community-focused sharing of Docker-based genomics tools and workflows [version 1; peer review: 2 approved]. F1000Research 2017, 6:52 (<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.10137.1>)

³⁷ Gustafsson, Ove Johan Ragnar. (2023, March 30). FAIR workflows. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7783773>

³⁸ Australian BioCommons WorkflowHub space <https://workflowhub.eu/programmes/8/workflows>

³⁹ ToolFinder https://australianbiocommons.github.io/2_tools.html

⁴⁰ Australian BioCommons Nextflow Tower service <https://australianbiocommons.github.io/tower/>

6. ABLeS access criteria and expectations

Each eligible ABLeS project has certain characteristics. The different project types are firstly characterised by a unique output. For Reference, Production and Software projects these are creation of reference data supporting downstream research, outputs supporting specific research questions or aims, and best practice bioinformatics software, respectively.

All ABLeS projects should also have a common research theme, a single project lead and a community-level decision making mechanism. Projects should also make efforts to carefully plan their usage of finite ABLeS resources, aim to develop and optimise their approaches to achieve best practice, and plan to share their outputs. For more detail see [Table 2](#).

There are also expectations related to either the project itself or its outputs when making use of an ABLeS project allocation ([Table 3](#)). Projects are expected to draw on community-level expertise (life science domain specific and bioinformatics), as well as engaging, collaborating and consulting with the BioCommons. Project contributors must also follow compute facility access policies, adhere to the time frame allocated for a project, and cite or acknowledge ABLeS as appropriate.

Ultimately, it is expected that any outputs from ABLeS projects will be broadly shared.

Examples include, the publication of reference data in a suitable repository (Reference project), documenting and versioning software code in a public repository and registering it such that it is FAIR (Accelerator project), and publication of results and / or methods (Production project, peer-reviewed or otherwise).

7. Case study - Genomics for Australian Plants

Genomics for Australian Plants (GAP)⁴¹ was initiated by Bioplatforms in partnership with researchers from the Australian State and National Herbarium and Botanic Gardens. The aim is to develop genomics resources to enhance the understanding of the evolution and conservation of the unique Australian flora.

Over the last couple of years, they have leveraged ABLeS resources to combine limited coverage genome sequencing to build the first-ever Australian Angiosperm Tree of Life: this is an evolutionary tree of nearly all Australian flowering plants, covering 1400 unique native plants. This is a foundational resource that will be used to support the classification of Australian angiosperms, conservation and management.

ABLeS supports this community through compute and storage allocations on Gadi⁴², the supercomputer available at NCI, and specialised expertise provided by ABLeS and NCI teams.

⁴¹ Genomics for Australian Plants (GAP) <https://www.genomicsforaustralianplants.com/>

⁴² NCI HPC Systems <https://nci.org.au/our-systems/hpc-systems>

Table 2. Characteristics of an eligible ABLeS project

Principle	Characteristics of an ABLeS project	Project type		
		Reference Data	Production bioinformatics	Software Accelerator
Data centric outcomes	It is producing reference and derived data assets that will be published to enable use / reuse by others outside the community.	Yes	Yes	
Research centric outcomes	It is producing data assets and outputs that are critical to research projects and consortia making use of best practice production level bioinformatics approaches.		Yes	
Software centric outcomes	It is creating, developing, installing, testing and/or optimising software that will be made available for use / reuse by others in the life science community.			Yes
Common research theme	It is a defined cross-institutional collaboration, project, community, consortium, or some other collaborative construct, that is focused on a common research theme.	Yes		
Development & optimisation	Communities work to understand their software, methods and the optimal approaches to solving the bioinformatics problems at hand. ABLeS will facilitate both the experimental / testing and production phases of computational analyses.	Yes		
Planned usage of ABLeS resources	The use of ABLeS resources is planned and approached with a level of care appropriate to their status as limited and consumable resources.	Yes		
Sharing	Appropriate mechanisms are used to share outputs that support and assist other communities, with examples provided in Table 3 . Outputs include software, methods, training, resource usage and quality assessments for derived reference data sets, submissions to data international repositories and research publications.	Yes		

Table 3. Expectations

Principle	Description	Project type		
		Reference Data	Production bioinformatics	Software Accelerator
Project leadership	A project lead is responsible for all use of resources provided, which will need to adhere to relevant facility processes and policies. The lead will also monitor and manage reasonable usage of their project computational infrastructure allocations.	Yes		
Community-level decision making	There exists a collaborative decision making mechanism to prioritise the bioinformatics work using relevant computational resources. This can be a formalised steering committee, a working group, or some other forum which is representative of the collaboration. Resources used must be agreed upon / in line with the community's decision making mechanism and align with community priorities.	Yes		
Community-level expertise	The community has expertise which will drive and execute its bioinformatics agenda. This expertise offers a strong collaboration link with the expertise and support available through ABLeS, NCI and Pawsey.	Yes		
Collaboration & consultation	ABLeS is collaborative and involves the BioCommons, the research community, and the computational facilities. It is also a standing item for discussion and forums play a strong role in managing the use of ABLeS: communities will thus engage the BioCommons in an open and collaborative manner, with regular meetups.	Yes		
Follow compute facility access policies	All users must abide by the relevant access policies of Pawsey and NCI. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NCI Terms and Conditions of Access; • NCI Data Collections Management; and • Pawsey Conditions of Access 	Yes		
Time frame / duration of allocations	Each project is reviewed at the 6 month mark, to ensure resources are being used as efficiently as practical and so challenges can be identified / addressed by the ABLeS team. Reference data and production projects are by definition on-going, while software accelerator projects need to be renewed at 6 months if the work originally described for the project has not been completed.	Ongoing Review every 6 months	Ongoing Review every 6 months	Limited to 6 month projects

Citing and acknowledging ABLeS	<p>The ABLeS program should be both cited and acknowledged in any publication, presentation or grant application.</p> <p>Cite the ABLeS publication (see below) in any manuscript, publication, presentation or grant application that was supported by data or services provided by ABLeS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manos, Steven, Gustafsson, Ove Johan Ragnar, Al Bkhetan, Ziad, & Francis, Rhys. (2022). Building community data assets for life sciences through ABLeS - the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (1.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6342352 <p>Use the following acknowledgement statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “The authors acknowledge the provision of computing and data resources provided by the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (ABLeS) program. This program is co-funded by Bioplatforms Australia (enabled by NCRIS), the National Computational Infrastructure and Pawsey Supercomputing Centre.” 	Yes		
Publication of reference data in a suitable repository	At a suitable time (e.g. immediately, post-publication) reference data outputs should be submitted to a relevant international data repository (e.g. European Nucleotide Archive [ENA ⁴³], MetaboLights ⁴⁴).	Yes	Optional	Optional
Availability of software code via a public repository	Software created or modified as part of an ABLeS project should be made available in a suitable public repository. The recommended option is GitHub ⁴⁵ . However, any platform that allows for public sharing of source code and version control can be used.	Yes	Requirement to start	Yes (60% resource usage)
Licensing	Software should be licensed for reuse, ideally with an open source license. See https://choosealicense.com/ .	Yes	Yes	Yes
Software documented and registered	<p>Software should be documented and registered on an appropriate platform. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workflows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dockstore https://dockstore.org/ WorkflowHub https://workflowhub.eu/ Software: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zenodo https://zenodo.org/ bio.tools https://bio.tools/ 	Yes	Requirement to start	Yes
Publication of results and/or methods	The publication of results, reference data, software or methods that are created as part of an ABLeS project is encouraged, particularly for production allocations which are focused on research centric outcomes.	Optional	Yes	Optional

⁴³ European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

⁴⁴ MetaboLights <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>

⁴⁵ GitHub <https://github.com/>

